

Can Negative Emotions Somehow Molded to Produce Constructive Decision Making? (*A mediation and moderation analysis*)

¹Azhar khan PhD Scholar

Department of Management Sciences Islamic College Peshawar, Pakistan

Corresponding author: azhar5896081@gmail.com

²Dr. Shahid Jan Kaka Khail (Associate Professor)

Chairman Department of Management Sciences Islamic College Peshawar, Pakistan

³Dr. Fayaz Ali Shah (Assistant Professor)

Department of Management Sciences Islamic College Peshawar, Pakistan

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Abstract: The current study is designed to enhance the concept that when and how negative emotions sparks proactivity with the influence of **reason-to**, **can-do** and **energize-to** motivational factors in order to replace the consequences of negative emotions into positive outcomes. Negative emotions at workplace are usually connected with destructive decision making. In this connection, numerous theories such as theories of emotions, theory of planned behavior, theory of self-efficacy, theory of proactive behavior and theory of decision making was studied with the aim to develop a convincing conceptual model in order to shape the destructive fallouts of discrete negative emotions into constructive decision making. In doing this, nine variables including independent variables, dependent variable, mediating variables and moderating variables were identified from the literature of reputed journals. Research objectives, research questions and hypotheses, about how each variable is connected with one another, were framed. Related scales were identified from the articles and research dissertations. Due to the burning issues related to the negative emotions and its consequences in shape of negative decision making concerning with education sector; it was decided that public sector universities of KP, Pakistan will be the target population. Only faculty members of the public sector of KP will be included to examine the newly developed conceptual framework of the present study. Due to the complex model of the current study, SEM-PLS will be the appropriate as analysis tool will be employed in order to test the hypotheses.

Key words: Proactive behavior, self-efficacy, protective effort, co-worker support, emotion regulation knowledge, pro-social motivation, constructive decision making.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

In recent decades, there has been a surge in research on negative emotions and decision making, with a focus on self-efficacy, emotion regulation knowledge, proactive behaviour, and pro-social motivation (Gross, 2015). Indeed, many scholars and practitioners now believe that emotions are the primary motivator for the majority of expressive decisions in life (Ekman, 2007). Many people, including Griffin (2006), believe that decision making should be free of emotion. In reality, negative emotions are commonly associated with negative behaviours and outcomes. Our emotions shape who we are; they are the driving force behind many behaviours, and there are so many other descriptive labels in our languages that lead to destructive decision making. According to Averill (1980), there are 550 words in English that relate to the word emotions, but people have difficulty explaining their emotions to others (Zajonc, 1980). An emotion is a highly personal and subjective experience defined as a feeling or state that is accompanied by behavioural, physiological, and cognitive mechanisms (Carlson & Hatfield, 1992). Human emotions are observed on three levels. Emotions are observed on a biological level as states of motivation involving changes in heart rate, breathing rate, and other physiological changes. It is related to different feeling states such as anger, fear, love, and pain and how they influence a person's perception, thinking, and behaviour on a psychological level. Coleman (1979) considers social level emotions to be a universal language centered on human expressions.

Positive and negative emotions are the two types of emotions that exist in the workplace. Positive emotions in the workplace help employees achieve positive outcomes such as constructive decision making, accomplishments, job commitment, and loyalty, whereas negative emotions produce unfavorable situations such as increased counter-productivity or uncivil behaviour, interpersonal conflicts, limited employees' efforts toward organisational improvement, and limited creativity and initiative (Lebel, 2017, Ashkanasy & Dorris, 2017; Maitlis & Ozcelik, 2004; Morrison & Miliken, 2000; Spector & Fox, 2002 & Anderson & Pearson, 1999). The claim of discrete emotion theory is that there are only a few core emotions. Silvan Tomkins (1962), for example, came to the conclusion that there are eight basic emotions: surprise, interest, joy, anger, fear, disgust, shame, and sorrow. Carroll Izard of the University of Delaware recently critically outlined 12 distinct emotions labelled: Interest, Joy, Surprise, Sadness, Anger, Disgust, Contempt, Self-Hostility, Fear, Shame, Shyness, and Guilt (Izard et al., 1993; Ashkanasy & Dorris, 2017).

Many academics believe that negative emotions (anger, fear) only have negative consequences, such as increased counter-productive or uncivil behaviour, interpersonal conflicts, limited employees' efforts toward organisational improvement, limited contextual performance, and limited creativity/initiative (Lebel, 2017, Ashkanasy & Dorris, 2017; Maitlis & Ozcelik, 2004; Morrison & Miliken, 2000; Spector & Fox, 2002 & Anderson & Pearson, 1999). Accordingly, prior researchers believe that emotions are the primary motivators for the majority of life's significant decisions (Ekman 2007; Lerner 2010 & Keltner et al 2014). Carlsmith and Gross (1969) state that emotions guide choices in order to avoid or reduce negative feelings such as regret, anger, or fear, while increasing or tolerating positive feelings such as pride and happiness (Dunn & Norton 2013), and even negative feelings such as fear and anger (Tracy & Robins 2007). According to (Coughlan & Connolly 2001, Mellers 2000), when the outcomes of our decisions manifest, we frequently experience new emotions such as (surprise, delight and or regret). Emotions and decision making, according to researchers, go hand in hand, at least when outcomes are important.

Thinking about change is a sign of proactive behaviour; employees who are experiencing negative emotions are ultimately driving themselves towards change, which is an anticipatory action aimed at oneself or the situation (Grant, 2000; Grant & Ashford, 2008). Employees who are proactive act in advance rather than reacting. They take steps to improve themselves and/or the situation (Grant & Ashford, 2008). Individually, proactive behaviour is discretionary but foreseen (Parker et al., 2010). When employees are proactive, they usually intend to be constructive and make a difference (Grant & Ashford, 2008). Speaking up with suggestions (Detert & Burris, 2007), selling issues to top management (Ashford, Rothbard, Piderit, & Dutton, 1998), taking charge or initiative by introducing new policies, procedures, or practices (Frese & Fay, 2001; Morrison & Phelps, 1999), and seeking feedback about performance and job status are all common characteristics of pro-activity (Ashford, 1986). As a result, pro-activity entails deliberate, motivated, and goal-oriented behaviour planning and execution (Grant & Ashford, 2008; Parker et al., 2010). Various models of pro-activity on the threshold of notions show that three motivational states of a person precede the planning and execution of proactive behaviour. First, employees determine whether or not proactivity is feasible, including efficacy assessments (i.e., can I do it?). The other is control, or whether it is feasible. Parker, Williams, and Turner (2006); Frese and Fay, 2001. Second, employees evaluate whether proactivity is worthwhile in terms of achieving relevant goals or expressing values (Grant & Rothbard, 2013; Morrison & Phelps, 1999). The third is emotional states, which provide energy to act ahead of time and persist in overcoming change barriers; all of these can fuel proactive efforts for employees (Bindl et al., 2012). These three proactive motivational states are known as can-do, reason-to, and energized-to motivation (Parker et al., 2010).

Those who have studied the relationship between negative emotions and pro-activity have tentatively developed arguments that suggest either negative or positive effects, as the effect is generally conceptualized as a natural emotional experience, e.g. mood, negative trait affect (Bindl, Parker, Totterdell, & Hagger-Johnson, 2012; Parker, Bindl, & Strauss, 2010). Only a few studies have looked at the relationship between negative emotions and proactivity, and the results have been mixed and inconsistent, with most pointing to a positive relationship (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2007), a negative relationship (Fritz, Yankelevich, Zarubin, & Barger, 2010; Fay & Sonnentag, 2012), or no relationship at all (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2007; Fritz & Sonnentag, 2009; Bindl et al., 2012). These contradictory arguments and inconsistencies in empirical findings suggest that organizational scholars lack a systematic understanding of whether and when negative affective experience influences proactive behaviour.

It is important to empirically test the theory that would explore the discrete emotions rather than the exaggerated emotional experiences to understand how negative emotions may spark pro-activity. Discrete emotions, such as anger and fear, are the result of a unique assessment of events and are associated with specific cognitions and behaviours, such as motivational goals and action tendencies. However, pro-activity researchers ignore a predictive approach by summarizing negative emotional experiences while ignoring the accompanying processes and behaviours (Barsade & Gibson, 2007; Gooty, Gavin & Ashkanasay, 2009; Ashkanasay & Humphrey, 2017; Lebel, 2017). These various points of view provide a theoretical foundation for identifying which discrete negative emotions (anger, fear) in contrast to negative affective experience in general, might spark pro-actively, and under what conditions they might do so.

1.2 Broader Problem Area

The majority of employees and organizations in developing countries are in similar situations. Many factors are directly related to destructive decision making due to negative emotions, and these negative emotions are caused by stress and workplace conflict, workplace bullying, harassment, conflicts with leadership/coworkers/customers, financial crisis within the organization, injustice, excessive workload, nepotism, lack of perceived organisational support, real or apparent threat at the workplace, technological change, poor work environment physicochemical This is especially true in Pakistan, where inflation, unemployment, political instability, and pandemics such as (Covid-19 and Dengue) are at an all-time high. In relation to other issues, for instance, coronavirus pandemic and its consequences, such as salary deductions, the elimination of some allowances, increased student fees, and instructions to charge fees from children of university teachers enrolled in universities, schools, and colleges. To avoid pension burden, the higher education sector is advised not to appoint employees on BPS. With these emotional and stressful situations causing negative emotions such as anger and fear among the faculty of public sector universities, almost every year, the teachers and employees of public sector universities announce pen-down strikes in all universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to protest against top-level decisions. In response to the strikes, police used baton charges and tear gas on public sector university teachers who were protesting the decisions in front of the provincial Assembly in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. According to police, at least eight of the protesting teachers were arrested for obstructing traffic. Such discriminatory impressions and heinous decisions were witnessed for the first time in the history of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's public sector universities, prompting leaders of the Federation of All Pakistan Universities Academic Staff Associations (FAPUASA) to join the protest and condemn the act of violence against teachers. Following these humiliating events and the waste of students' valuable time for more than a week, FAPUASA has demanded the dismissal of the head Academic Search Committee, the establishment of a provisional Higher Education Commission, and the withdrawal of notification related to salary and pension deductions for university faculty.

In line with the issues, the same financial issues, university reforms including allowance reductions, and issues related to workload of university teachers were raised every year, and finally pen-drop strikes against the administration of public sector universities were announced.

Almost every year, the academic staff and faculty of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's public sector universities threaten to go on strike and observe 'World Teachers Day' as a 'Black Day' (Federation of All Pakistan Universities Academic Staff Association) (FAPUASA). Teachers' unions became enraged over the employees' protest and broke classroom locks when the decision to raise their salaries was not implemented.

As everyone knows, students are the most important stakeholders in universities, and no action such as university closure should be taken by employees. Other workplace issues related to these negative factors have an impact on the people of Pakistan, particularly educational institutions to which millions of people (both teachers and students) are directly attached. In such a situation, extracting positive outcomes from negative built-up emotions is not only a difficult task, but it also carries more weight-age to drive the state in a difficult situation of an emerging economy. Negative emotions, such as fear, anger, stress, hostility, sadness, and guilt, on the other hand, increase the predictability of workplace deviance as well as how the organization is perceived by the outside world. However, the teacher's union attempted to persuade the employees to end the strike but was unsuccessful due to the high level of negative emotions.

It is widely acknowledged that negative emotions frequently have a negative impact on organizations by increasing counterproductive or uncivil behaviour and limiting employees' efforts toward organisational improvement, resulting in poor decision making. Up to this point, research has focused on the effects of negative emotions on an individual's and an organization's productivity. However, it has not yet been investigated how these negative emotions can be put to use, so that they can be molded by some technique/mechanism to play a role in promoting constructive decision making in both the individual and the organization as a whole. What has been lacking to date is convincing that a conceptual framework will enable researchers to understand the process of when and how negative emotions can spark proactive behaviour and how it can be molded to produce a positive outcome.

1.2.1. Problem statement

For a long time, there has been a growing problem of negative emotions and destructive decision-making in KP's public sector universities. Anger and fear are two possible causes of this problem. While the majority of previous research has yielded mixed results, these negative discrete emotions (such as anger and fear) have an impact on the overall productivity of public sector universities and overall academic performance. Because of teacher strikes and protests against high-ups and their decisions, this problem has had a negative impact on students and their studies. In this regard, the area under investigation by researchers is negative emotions, and the problem is that while researchers have been able to analyze the impact of negative emotions on individual and organisational decision making, few studies have been conducted on the possibility that negative emotions can be molded to produce positive outcomes, such as constructive decision making. Various researchers have suggested that universities investigate the underlying mechanism by which anger and fear can lead to positive outcomes (proactive behaviour) and subsequent decision-making, so that universities can overcome the negative effects of negative discrete emotions (Lebel, 2017).

The question that previous researchers were unable to answer concretely was how to develop a more suitable model that could mold negative discrete emotions into positive outcomes and constructive decision making. According to the source, several litigation cases have been filed in Pakistan's lower and higher courts, including the Supreme Court, due to negative emotions and their consequences in the form of incorrect or harsh decision-making, which has resulted in the loss of the image of universities and their faculties, as well as the loss of time for the country's judicial system. Now, the researcher's focus is on negative emotions, and the problem is that no one has yet been able to analyze the effects of these negative emotions on organizational performance, particularly in KP's public sector universities.

Pen drop strikes and pressure on high-ups to boycott classes are the results of negative emotions of individuals leading to destructive decisions, resulting in a waste of time and money in universities. According to (Khan, 2013), teachers' associations and representatives of public sector universities from across the province claimed that discrete emotions and their consequences compelled university administrations to raise issues with the provincial government or, in some cases, to go to court. So far, fewer studies have been conducted on the possibility that negative emotions can be manipulated to produce positive outcomes, such as proactive decision-making (Lebel, 2017). Various researchers have suggested that we investigate the underlying mechanism by which anger and fear can lead to proactive behaviour, which then leads to a positive outcome (e.g., constructive decision making). Anger and fear, according to Lebel (2017), can energize employees at work by instilling self-efficacy and protective effort, with the ultimate goal

of preparing them to engage in proactive behaviour. There are hints that a negative emotional experience at work can drive self-starting proactive behaviour, according to (Frese & Fay, 2001). The goal of this study is to test and understand an empirical model that investigates when and how negative emotions lead to proactive behaviour. However, until now, there has been a lack of a solid theoretical framework that will allow us to comprehend the mechanisms of mediating and moderating analysis, as well as the processes that underpin this seemingly inconsistent condition.

1.3 Purpose of the study:

The primary goal of the study is to focus on two distinct negative emotions, anger and fear, for three reasons. To begin, anger and fear have a strong influence on work behaviour, and both are widely perceived to have destructive and counter-productive consequences, such as destructive decision making (Fox & Spector, 1999; Kish-Gephart, Detert, Trevino & Edmondson, 2009). Second, both anger and fear are symbols of negatively perceived, intense/deep emotions that encourage the employee to take either present or future actions, which becomes a source of energy and motivation to act pro-actively (Lerner & Keltner, 2001; Frijda, 1986; Smith & Ellsworth, 1985, Lebel, 2017). Finally, because anger and fear differ in many ways, the goal of this research is to develop and test a theory that describes when anger and fear may lead to proactive behaviour. Appraisals of events that elicit anger and fear, as well as behavioural responses to these emotions, vary. Anger, for example, is triggered by perceptions of high certainty and control, and it is associated with "fight," approach, and behavioural tendencies, whereas fear is triggered by perceptions of low certainty and control. Fear is commonly associated with "flight" or avoidance behaviour (Ellsworth & Scherer, 2003; Frijda, Kuiper's, & terSchure, 1989; Lebel, 2017). These distinctions highlight the importance of adopting a discrete negative emotion perspective, which allows for a more defined understanding of the factors and mechanisms underlying functional responses to negative emotions. Lazarus and Cohencharash (2001); Lindebaum and Jordan (2012); Ashkansay (2016)

Not every situation involving anger and fear is the same; the response to such discrete emotions can vary depending on the situation. Fear, for example, can cause withdrawal, freezing in place, defensive effort, and increased attention (Frijda, 1986; Ohman, 2008), whereas anger can cause revengeful/unforgiving or harmful behaviour, venting/expelling to a third party, withdrawal, or constructive problem resolution (Lerner & Tedens, 2006).

This study extended the work of Lebel (2017) by applying the perspective of discrete emotions to the domain of proclivity, and proposed a contingent/depending model that would identify the circumstances under which the experience of anger or fear would lead to proactive behaviour, which would lead to constructive outcomes, i.e. decision making. This study would look at the problem through the lens of proactive behaviour theory, focusing specifically on the discrete negative emotions of anger and fear (Parker, Bindl, & Strauss, 2010). Anger and fear may energize employees with efficacy and protective effort, respectively, preparing them to be proactive, and this proclivity may result in constructive outcomes, such as decision making. According to this study, when employees believe they can or have a reason to act ahead of time, these energized states may lead to proactive behaviour.

This study's proposed model makes several significant theoretical and empirical contributions. To begin, scholars have debated that the role of negative emotions in pro-activity is significant but under-hypothesized (Bindl & Parker, 2012, Grant & Ashford, 2008, Ashkanasay, 2016, Lebel, 2017). However, there are

indications that negative emotional experiences can lead to proactive self-starting behaviours. Its goal is to gain a better understanding of when and why this phenomenon occurs. Second, this study may contribute to the theory of emotions in organizations by defining when negative emotions, such as fear and anger, produce positive outcomes at work. Third, if employees experience anger and fear, and if proactive behaviour can improve the performance of individuals and organizations as a whole, then understanding how these negative discrete emotions shape pro-activity adds value to an organization. The preceding arguments provide practical insight into how leaders, supervisors, and employees can effectively manage negative emotional experiences in the presence of anger or fear, and thus increase proactive behaviour that leads to constructive outcomes (decision making).

1.4 Gap Analysis

After a thorough investigation, it was discovered that emotions and their outcomes have a lot of potential, resulting in positive emotions supporting constructive outcomes and negative emotions supporting destructive outcomes. Many academics believe that negative emotions such as anger and fear can have negative consequences such as poor decision-making, increased counter-productivity or uncivil behaviour, interpersonal conflicts, limiting employees' efforts to improve the organization, limiting contextual performance, and limiting creativity (Lebel, 2017, Ashkanasy & Dorris, 2017, Maitlis & Ozelik, 2004; Spector & Fox, 2002; Morrison & Miliken, 2000; Anderson & Pearson, 1999). After a thorough analysis of the literature, gaps have been depicted as a result of the research.

1.4.1 Theoretical Gap Analysis

1.4.1.1. Gap in discrete negative emotions (anger and fear) with constructive decision making

A theoretical gap exists, when there is no established theory existing in literature. In this research study, the first gap is going to highlight that there is a need for a cogent/ convincing theoretical framework that enables the researcher to understand the processes underlying this seemingly inconsistent situation **and how the experience of anger and fear leads to constructive decision making**. Ashkanasy (2017) suggests that negative emotions can also play a positive role in promoting pro-activity. In this connection, a convincing conceptual framework with the support of theory is missing to date to understand the process of molding negative emotions into positive decision making.

1.4.1.2 Gap in systematic understanding of when and how negative emotions sparks pro-activity

According to Lebel (2017), further research may explore the role of negative emotions influencing pro-activity (Parker, Bindl, & Strauss, 2010; Parker, Totterdell, & Hagger-Johnson, 2012), broadly conceptualizing a stable dispositional or state of emotional experience that affect behavior and mood. In prior studies, the examination of relationship between negative emotions and pro-activity, scholars have produced mixed and inconsistent findings, frequently suggesting a positive relationship (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2007), a negative relationship (Fritz, Yankelevich, Zarubin, & Barger, 2010; Fay & Sonnentag, 2012), or no relationship (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2007; Fritz & Sonnentag, 2009; Bindl *et al.*, 2012). These competing arguments and inconsistent empirical results suggest that organizational scholars lack a systematic understanding of whether and when negative emotional experience influences proactive behavior which leads to produce positive outcomes. In this connection, there is a need for a model consisting underpinning support of theories that make a sense that when and how negative emotions such as anger

and fear sparks proactive behavior. Prior research emphasizes on mediation and moderation effects with the concept of negative emotions and positive outcomes.

1.5 Contextual Gap Analyses

According to Lebel (2017), the phenomena of discrete negative emotions requires study in different organizational contexts with different cultures of employees in order to investigate when and how negative emotions lead to proactive behavior. Many researchers studying negative emotions in organizations also suggested paying more attention to the role played by the context, especially in the cross-culture. For instance, Li *et al.* (2010) employed a large sample from Mainland China for a study on overall organizational commitment related to certain emotions in an organizational setting. As per the findings, the past theories from western samples presented that the **multilevel model of affective emotion theory** is broadly applicable. Moreover, another study of Li *et al.* (2016) found that responses to emotional upset are diverse across the samples of the United States and China. Similarly, Vogel *et al.* (2015) found cross-cultural differences in subordinate perceptions of abusive supervision. Based on these findings, and given the pervasiveness of multinational enterprises, researchers should give priority to studying topics across all levels of emotions in organizations in multi-cultural contexts. Additionally, Li *et al.* (2010) pointed out that collectivistic versus individualistic natured team members can considerably influence the affective dynamics of a team (Wagner & Iles 2008).

1.6 Methodological Gap

A researcher can develop a theory with the fundamental logical assumptions on a specified phenomenon by applying new methodology to accept or reject research hypotheses on the bases of research outcomes; this is called a methodological gap.

1.7 Empirical Gap

A gap in research actually means the limitation of current study, while the empirical gap describes a theory, concept or phenomenon. Empirical gap exists when the relationships of the study do not testify or are not verified in prior studies. In this study, many relationships between the variables are tested for the first time in a complex model in order to understand empirical knowledge as well as to fill the empirical gap. In this research study, a complex model consisting of three mediating and three moderating variables makes a sense that empirical gaps exist and need to be tested for the confirmation.

1.8 Knowledge Gap

In research, a knowledge gap is an inconsistency and disagreement between what is known and what needs to be known. This knowledge gap can be filled through tackling previous research studies to identify what is missing in either literature, theory, or in methodology in general. A knowledge gap can be filled by doing new research studies based on identified gaps from the previous studies. In this research study, the researcher is interested to discover the knowledge gap regarding negative emotions and its relationships with constructive outcomes. Not only this, the intention of the researcher in this study is to explain the

mechanism of mediation and moderation related to the negative emotions, pro-activity and constructive decision making.

1.9 Conceptual Gap

As the name suggests, a gap that relates to abstract concepts and ideas. A conceptual gap exists when it does not involve real-world experimentation but as an alternative relies on information available in prior studies on a given area. A conceptual gap arises when there is some cognitive model of the claim and how the claim actually works. In this research study, a conceptual model or a framework is initially used to outline the possible courses of action. In this connection, a conceptual model is developed based on the literature in a logical manner which provides a rigor to the process of research.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theory of Emotions

Theory of evolution motivates humans to respond rapidly and positively in order to improve the chances of accomplishment (Darwin, 2000).

2.2 Cognitive Appraisal Theory

This theory has a great concern with intellectuals and rationales. According to Lazarus (the pioneer of cognitive theory), thinking must happen first before experiencing emotions. This theory of emotion is also referred to as Lazarus theory of emotions. This theory of emotion occurs in a sequence. First motivation is involved, followed by thoughts, which then leads to the experience of physiological reactions of emotion such as anger and fear.

2.3 Appraisal Tendency Theory

The appraisal tendency framework explains why and how emotions affect decisions at workplace. On the other hand, negative emotions are related to criticizing the consequences. Fair decision can be affected by emotions based on appraisals of control (Lerner, Han & Keltner, 2007).

2.4 Cognitive functional model

Nabi (1999) gave a different perspective on how emotions affect decision making which is known as cognitive functional model. This model states that each of the five discrete emotions (anger, fear, disgust, shame, and guilt) leads to an action tendency: such as fear tends to lead to avoidance, whereas anger helps 'mobilize and sustain high levels of energy for the purpose of defending oneself and loved ones, or correcting some appraised wrong' or removing a barrier to a goal. Once an emotion is experienced, two motivations emerge simultaneously, these are: motivated processing and motivated attention (Nabi, 1999, 2002). Theorists also proposed that basic emotions have regulatory characteristics and they modulate cognition and action (Lundvist & Ohman, 2005; Merker, 2007), these changes also affect emotions (Cole, Martin, & Dennis, 2004; Camos, Frankel, & Camras, 2004).

2.5 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

In psychology, the theory of planned behavior (abbreviated TPB) is a theory that links beliefs and behaviors. The concept was proposed by Icek Ajzen to improve the predictive power of the theory of reasoned action by including perceived behavioral control. **There are so many reasons for these emotions which include**

the fear of job-loss, bad reputation, quantitative role conflict and vulnerability to be criticized by the general masses. These experienced anger and fear, affect the cognitive patterns of the affected. Here comes the role of different proactive behaviors that reduce the negative effects of experienced anger and fear. Parker *et al* (2006) concluded that employees behave pro-actively if they are convinced that the benefits of exercising proactive behaviors will offset risks and harms related to it, but how this interplay of experienced anger and fear become antecedents of proactive behaviors, along with protective efforts (which are positive behaviors) facilitate the positive job outcome i.e. decision making.

2.6 Emotion Imbued Choice Model (EICM)

According to Lerner *et al.* (2015), EICM is a standard trying to attempt how emotions infuse choice and decision process. The aim of this model was to create classical and newly emotional input to describe conscious and unconscious decision making by mixing determinants and magnitudes of emotions.

A schematic model of emotion inputs in judgment and decision making drawn from the Emotion-Imbued Choice Model by Lerner *et al.*

2.7 The real-time effect at work

An ignored phenomenon in organizational behavior; alternatively, if you were unfairly instructed by your manager, the negative emotions you experience may cause you to withdraw from work or to act mean toward a coworker. Over time, these small moments of emotion on the job can influence a person's decision making. Although company perks and promotions can contribute to a person's happiness at work, satisfaction is not simply a result of this kind of "outside-in" reward system. Job satisfaction in the AET model comes from the inside-in—from the combination of an individual's personality, small emotional experiences at work overtime, beliefs, and affect-driven behaviors.

Correspondingly, experienced anger and fear affect the cognitive patterns of the effects. Here comes the role of different proactive behaviors that reduce the negative effects of experienced anger and fear. Parker *et al.* (2006) concluded that employees behave pro-actively if they are convinced that the benefits of exercising proactive behaviors will balance risks and harms related to it, but how this chemistry of experienced anger and fear becomes antecedents of proactive behaviors, along with protective efforts (which are positive behaviors) facilitating the positive outcome i.e. decision making? This needs empirical analysis based on AET which will explain the mechanism through which the negatives of fear and anger is balanced by proactive behaviors and how these proactive behaviors indirectly influence (via protective efforts) positive job outcome i.e. decision making.

2.8 Theory of Self-Efficacy

The theory of self-efficacy is described as people's beliefs in their competences to work out and control over their own functioning and over events that affect their lives. According to the founder of self-efficacy theory, Bandura (1997), one's sense of self-efficacy can provide the foundation for motivation, well-being, and personal accomplishment. A self-efficacy states that it is an individual's belief on his or her abilities to control emotions in order to produce positive outcomes at the workplace. Self-efficacy reproduces confidence and control over negative emotions in order to motivate an individual's behavior to perform pro-actively (Bandura, 1977).

2.9 Theory of Pro-activity

The theory of pro-activity refers to the self-initiated behavior that activates to control negative emotions and solves a problem before it has occurred. Proactive behavior contains anticipatory actions which avoid reaction for the sake of future situations. Beyond reacting to their workplace and desires people have the extraordinary capabilities to pro-actively set and pursue organizational goals.

2.10 Theory of Emotion Regulation

Emotion regulation is the ability to exert control over one's own emotional state. It may involve behaviors such as rethinking a challenging situation to reduce anger and fear or focusing on reasons to feel happy or calm. Emotion regulation involves reducing the intensity of negative emotions. The founder of emotion regulation, James Gross; a psychologist, emphasizes that individuals at the workplace can act to control their negative emotions at different points. On the other hand, Larsen and Prizmic (1999) state that emotion regulation is a process aimed at the expansion of positive emotions and minimization of negative emotions at the workplace which is also known as pleasure / hedonic emotion regulation. According to the theory of Gross (2014, 2015) that emotion regulation is a process in which employees influence what they have, and how they experience and express them. Gross (2014) further stated that emotions need not to be regulated or changed all the time but need to be regulated when they interfere with desired behavior or goals (Aldao et al., 2015; English et al., 2017).

Conceptual Framework of the study with support of several theories

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3. Research Methodology

Research methodology is a pattern of conducting research empirically in order to achieve the objectives of research. A research design is a systematic way to conduct a research. It has different phases. According to Saunders *et al.* (2007) research onion describes more detailed stages of the research process.

Source: Saunders *et al.*, (2007)

3.1 Population

In this study, the population frame is composed of all faculty members of 11 public sector Universities located at different districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Only those universities are included in the study that have attained the statutory age of 10 years or above. Below mentioned Universities are included in the research.

There are three criteria to choose the proper sample size. The level of certainty or chance, the level exactness and the level of inconstancy being measurement of quality (Israel, 1992).

3.2 Sample Size:

The sample size is derived from the formula given by Solvin's (1960) for a limited population with 95% Confidence Interval while 5% of error. Solvin's Formula is a good option for determining sample size in survey research especially in social sciences.

$$n = n = N \div (1 + Ne^2)$$

n = Sample size

N = Total Population

e = Error tolerance i.e. 5%

Table 1. Determination of Sample Size using Solvin's Formula

Population in Public Sector Universities (Faculty)	Total
$n = N/1+N*(e)^2$ $n=3157/ 1+3157*(.05)^2$	n = 355

3.3 Sampling

Sampling methods are adapted to choose a group of representative units from a population, observes Lim and Ting (2013). Probability and non-probability are the two sampling methods used in research studies. In probability sampling each individual in the population has given equivalent chances of being included in the sample whereas in non-probability sampling individuals do not have identical chances of being included (Levy and Lemeshow, 2013). Probability sampling is divided into simple random, cluster, systematic and stratified random sampling. On the other hand, non-probability sampling is classified into convenience, quota and purposive sampling.

Justification: In this research, the researcher will use a probability random sampling method for obtaining primary data from the faculty of public sector universities of KP, Pakistan.

Below mentioned tables show the name of universities, the total faculty members in each university, the percentage of faculty and finally the required sample as per the formula applied.

Table 2 Population and Sample size

Sr. #	Name of Universities	Faculty in		Sample Size	
		number	Percentage	in Number	Round
1	University of Peshawar	618	19.58	69.49	70
2	Gomal University D.I.Khan	543	17.20	61.06	61
3	Abdul Wali Khan University	425	13.46	47.79	48
4	Kohat University	298	9.44	33.51	34
5	Islamia College Peshawar	246	7.79	27.66	28

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6	Hazara University	245	7.76	27.55	28
7	Malakand University	186	5.89	20.92	21
8	IM Sciences, Peshawar	180	5.70	20.24	20
9	Frontier Women University	178	5.64	20.02	20
10	Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Shrinale	140	4.43	15.74	16
11	Karak University	98	3.10	11.02	11
TOTAL		3157	100	355	357
Sample Size		355			

Determination of Sample Size using Solvin's Formula

Population in Public Sector Universities (Faculty)	Total
$n = \frac{N}{1+N*(e)^2}$ $n = \frac{3157}{1+3157*(.05)^2}$	$n = 355$

3.4 Development of Instrument for fact finding

The collection of primary data from the faculty of eleven public sector universities is collected via adopted survey questionnaires. The questionnaire of this study is composed of ten (10) sections. Each section is given code such as A, B up to J. Section 'A' of the questionnaire covered demographic information. Section 'B' covered negative emotion (Anger) which is the first independent variable of the study. Section 'C' covered negative emotion (Fear) which is the second independent variable of the study. Section 'D' covered self-efficacy which is the first mediating variable of the study. Section 'E' covered protective effort which is the second mediating variable of the study. Section 'F' covered proactive behavior which is the third mediating variable of the study. Section 'G' covered co-worker support which is the first moderating variable of the study. Section 'H' covered emotion regulation knowledge which is the second moderating variable of the study. Section 'I' covered prosocial motivation which is the third moderating variable of the study. Finally, section 'J' covered constructive decision making which is the only dependent variable of the study.

3.5 Negative Emotion (Anger)

Anger is a highly activated and unpleasant emotion (Smith & Ellsworth, 1985). Prior studies perceived that anger is a negative emotion which may lead to destructive consequences (Lebel, 2017; Ashkanasy & Dorris, 2017). Seven items are adopted from the study of Arnold H. (1992), the example of items such as "I flare up quickly but get over it quickly", "When frustrated, I let my irritation show", "I sometimes feel like a powder keg ready to explode", "I am an even-tempered person", "Some of my friends think I'm a hothead", "Sometimes I fly off the handle for no good reason", "I have trouble controlling my temper". For these seven adopted items, five point Likert scale was used while the overall composite reliability of this adopted scale was 0.89.

3.6 Negative Emotion (Fear)

Fear is also an unpleasant emotion; it is an innate response that takes place in every human being Burchfield (1956). Similarly, Wenar and Kerig (2000) described fear as a normal reaction to an environmental threat. For the measurement of negative emotion (fear), five (5) items of fear were adopted from the study of Rogers and Kelloway (1997). The five items were adopted are “For fear of a verbal caution from my supervisor/ boss”, “For fear of a show cause/ warning letter of criticism from my supervisor/ boss”, “For fear that my supervisor/ bosses will watch and control me more closely”, “For fear that my organization will start disciplinary action with the intention of forbidding/ dismissing me”, “I’m afraid of being hit, kicked, grabbed, shoved, or pushed while I’m at work”. A five point Likert scale was used while Cronbach’s Alpha was found 0.801.

3.7 Self-Efficacy

A self-efficacy can be described as an individual belief in his/her abilities to accomplish behavior to perform desired fulfillment (Bandura, 1977, 1986, 1997). To measure self-efficacy, three items were adopted from the study of Caprara *et al.* (2008). The Cronbach’s Alpha were found 0.82 while a five point Likert scale has been used ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The three items adopted are “Avoid Flying off the handle when I get angry”, “Get over irritation quickly for wrongs I have experienced”, “Avoid getting upset when others keep giving me a hard time”.

3.8 Protective Effort

Protective effort can be described as increased focus on a threat and readiness for defensive action (Frijda, 1986; Izard & Ackerman, 2000). In this connection, five items were adopted from the study of Clark and Watson (1995). The Cronbach’s Alpha was found 0.834 while a five point Likert scale has been used ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The five items are “I can deal with whatever challenges come my way”, “I feel that I belong with my friends”, “My family is a source of strength for me”, “I believe in myself”, “I can rely on myself to be ready for what I need to do each day”.

3.9 Proactive behavior

Proactive behaviors can be described as “taking initiative in improving current conditions, as anticipatory, future or change-oriented, self-starting, persistent and desirable behaviors” (Crant, 2000; Parker *et al.*, 2006; Ohly and Fritz, 2007). In this connection, six items were adopted from the study of Ali Murat ALPARSLAN (2016). The Cronbach’s Alpha was found 0.85 while a five point Likert scale has been used ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The six items are “I encourage my colleagues to speak up their opinions explicitly which might be affecting in our work unit”, “I speak up or express my opinions about work issues even if my opinions are different from my colleagues or disagree with them”, “I speak up with my colleagues’ ideas or opinions explicitly for changes in this organization”, “I make recommendations or suggestions concerning issues that affect my colleagues’ career development”, “I spend a lot of time and effort social networking with my colleagues at work”, “I think that my large network of colleagues at work which developed myself facilitate implementation of work processes in organization”.

3.10 Co-worker support

Co-worker support can be defined as co-workers assisting each other in hard times when needed by sharing knowledge and moral support as providing courage and strength (Zhou and George, 2001). To measure co-worker support, the scale was adopted from the study of O'Driscoll (2000). The scale has a reliability of 0.89 and gets answers on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agreed). The adopted items are "Have the people working with me ever given any information or advice to me", "Have the people working with me ever understand me and given advice", "Has anyone given me clear and helpful feedback about my work", "Has anyone given me assistance in my work".

3.11 Emotion regulation knowledge

Emotion regulation knowledge is the ability of an individual to overcome negative emotions at the workplace. According to Gross, (2001) emotion regulation knowledge is what, individual think to handle their emotions in response to hazard and undesirable conditions.

To measure emotion regulation knowledge, the scale was adopted from the study of (Gross & John, 2003). The scale has a reliability of 0.789 and obtained the responses from the respondents on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly disagree). The adopted items are "When I want to feel less negative emotion (such as fear or anger), I change what I'm thinking about", "When I'm faced with a stressful situation, I make myself think about it in a way that helps me stay calm", "I control my emotions by changing the way I think about the situation I'm in", "When I am feeling negative emotions, I make sure not to express them", "When I want to feel less negative emotion, I change the way I'm thinking about the situation".

3.12 Prosocial Motivation

Prosocial motivation can be described as the desire to defend and promote the welfare and well-being of other co-workers at the workplace (Grant, 2008). To measure prosocial motivation, the scale was adopted from the study of Grant (2008). The scale has a reliability of 0.735 and obtained the answers on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The adopted items are "I get energized by working on tasks that have the potential to benefit others", "I like to work on tasks that have the potential to benefit others", "I prefer to work on tasks that allow me to have a positive impact on others", "I do my best when I'm working on a task that contributes to the well-being of others", "It is important to me to have the opportunity to use my abilities to benefit others".

3.13 Constructive decision making

Constructive outcomes come from a positive mind and a productive mind. Constructive decision making is the ability to choose between competing courses of action based on the relative subjective value of their probabilistic consequences.

To measure constructive decision making, the scale was adopted from the study of Evans, & Barchard, (2005). A 9 items The scale has a reliability of 0.857 and obtained the answers on a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The adopted items are "Listen to my heart rather than my brain", "Plan of my life based on how I feel", "Base my goal in life on inspiration rather than logic", "Listen to my emotions when making important life decision", "Believe emotions give directions to

life”, “Rarely consider my emotions when making decision”, “Plan my life logically”, “Believe important decisions should be based on logic”, “Make decision on facts, not emotions”.

4. Data Analysis

To determine the descriptive analysis, factor analysis, correlation, regression analysis, validity and reliability analysis, the researcher is intended to use (SMART PLS 3.3) Partial Least Squares (PLS).

When a study has to predict a collection of dependent variables from a wide number of independent variables, structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) comes in handy (Abdi, 2007). In comparison to other predictive multivariate approaches, this example demonstrates when researchers should utilize this methodology.

5. Conclusion:

This study aims to expand on the idea that when and how negative emotions spark proactivity with the help of reason-to, can-do, and energize-to motivational factors, the consequences of negative emotions can be replaced with positive outcomes. Negative emotions at work are frequently associated with poor decision making. Several theories, including theories of emotions, theories of planned behaviour, theories of self-efficacy, theories of proactive behaviour, and theories of decision making, were studied in this context with the goal of developing a convincing conceptual model to shape the destructive fallouts of discrete negative emotions into constructive decision making. In doing so, nine variables were identified from the literature of reputable journals, including independent variables, dependent variables, mediating variables, and moderating variables. The research objectives, research questions, and hypotheses regarding how each variable is related to one another were developed. Articles and research dissertations were used to identify related scales. Due to the burning issues related with negative emotions and its consequences at public sector universities since long, it was decided that public sector universities in KP, Pakistan, would be the target population. Only KP faculty members from the public sector will be included in the current study's examination of the newly developed conceptual framework. Due to the complexity of the current study's model, it was obvious that SEM-PLS would be used as an analysis tool to test the hypotheses.

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